

Take Us There: Building the Political Party Nigeria Never Had

The role of an ideologically based, purpose-driven, and policy-binding political party in the growth and development of any political system cannot be underestimated. No democratic society can thrive without the prevalence of purposeful political parties. Since Nigeria's return to democratic rule in 1999, the country has been grappling with issues of bad governance, corruption, and economic challenges, with resultant effects evident in more than 63% of its population classified as multidimensionally poor. Political party is the only veritable means through which political leaders are recruited in a democratic state. It must be capable of producing candidates who are competent in turning the fortune of a country for good. There is no way the greatest good can be delivered to the greatest number of Nigerians when prevailing political parties lack ideologies and are formed solely with the elite intent of wrestling political power for the advancement of self-interest.

Nigerian political parties.

From the People's Democratic Party (PDP) to the All Progressives Congress (APC), Nigeria has been ruled by different political parties without different results. The hurriedly set-up APC in 2013 emerged as a coalition party with the primary intent of displacing the PDP from power after 15 years of bad governance and correcting the ills. While the former succeeded and an incumbent president was defeated for the first time in Nigeria, its anti-people policies and lacklustre socio-economic strategies, coupled with internal political wranglings, have further worsened the situation of Nigeria. From currency devaluation pushing the naira to its all-time low (ATL) against dollar at 1850/\$ to inflation skyrocketing to 30%, removal of fuel subsidies

without a social safety net, and spending \$18 billion on turnaround maintenance of four moribund state refineries (only to later tinker with selling the refineries without financial transparency or achieving tangible results), among others, Nigerians are particularly frustrated. While salary earners are living from hand to mouth, with the increased minimum wage not matching socio-economic realities, there is growing unemployment at 5%, and underemployment is widespread. Yet, the political class is living in outright opulence—spending billions of naira on renovations (which are deemed inflated) and refusing to cut the cost of governance. For instance, the Federal Capital Territory Administration (FCTA) recently completed the Vice President's new residence for N21 billion and renovated the International Conference Center (ICC) for N39 billion. In the same vein, State governments are not left out, with the Oyo State Government shelving N63.4 billion to renovate the government house. Nigerians have been left in the lurch for so long and are in search of a viable alternative. Is it the ADC?

The recently announced opposition coalition, the African Democratic Congress (ADC), has been making headlines since its announcement on July 2, touting its intent to displace the APC-led government of President Bola Ahmed Tinubu in the 2027 general elections. Like preceding political parties, it vows to wrestle political power for the benefit of Nigerians. Yet, the political party is made up of familiar political figures who have contributed overtly or covertly to the poor socio-economic conditions of the country over the last two decades. One thing is peculiar to the three major political parties (APC, PDP, and ADC) in Nigeria: they were formed by virtually the same set of people—propelled by a similar situation—being disgruntled—and a similar mission—hijack power. It is worthy to recall that the disgruntled members of the PDP, led by the then Minister of Transportation, Rotimi Ameachi, left the PDP for APC on the eve of the 2015 election after claiming to be marginalized. The same journey was travelled by the former Vice President, Alhaji Atiku Abubakar, from the PDP to the APC in 2014, and later back to the PDP in 2017. This same set of people also felt disgruntled and marginalized in the APC and formed the ADC with the intent of rescuing Nigerians. Historical antecedents show that Nigerians need to be wary of them. Without any sense of amnesia, political parties are recycling old political figures who have already demonstrated their full potential, which is insufficient to propel the country. If there is to be meaningful progress, the basis of political party formations and the rules governing them should be amended and rooted in strong political ideas.

In the current 10th National Assembly, 32 members of the House of Representatives and 6 senators have defected from the platforms they were elected to other political parties in just 2 years without forfeiting their seats. While section 68(1)(g) of the Nigerian Constitution prohibits a member of the Senate or House of Representatives from defecting to another political party without losing their seat, there is an exception that supports defection if it is due to a division within the original political party or a merger of political parties. The ambiguous definition of 'division' has been exploited by many political office holders to game the electorate. Once they win an election on a political platform, they spend most of the administrative years preparing for

the next election and won't hesitate to switch political parties at will. This is not practicable in developed democracies, where political ideas are well entrenched. In the United States, the two major political parties, Democrat and Republican are ideologically driven. While the former is known for modern liberalism, civil rights, and social inclusions, the latter is known for conservatism, free-market capitalism, and strong national defense. Despite the close ties between President Donald Trump and his billionaire friend Elon Musk, the latter resigned from Trump's administration as leader of the Department of Government Efficiency (DOGE) and has threatened to create a third party known as the American Party if Trump's domestic policy bill becomes law because it would add trillions of dollars to the federal deficit. That's healthy ideological rivalry that is much needed in the Nigerian political arena.

There is no gainsaying that the political party Nigeria never had was one driven by sheer political ideas of the common good for the people. More than at any other time, the coalition opposition, ADC, has to prove itself worthy of Nigerians' trust. To serve as an alternative path, it must operate on internal democracy, policy-driven campaigns, and zero accommodation of godfatherism. It must pave the way for young, competent Nigerians from the six geo-political zones who are capable of propelling the country to greater heights through knowledge of digital economy, technology, education reform, sustainable development, and citizen-centric policies. We must rise above the old order, and ensure political parties serve as vehicles for delivering the greatest good to the greatest number of Nigerians.

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